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CONDITIONS AND FACTORS IN THE PROCESS OF THE EMERGENCE OF THE EARLY STATES IN THE TERRITORY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: This article examines the critical conditions and factors that contributed to the emergence of early states in the territory of Uzbekistan. The study provides a detailed analysis of socio-political, economic, and cultural influences shaping the formation of early states in Uzbekistan. Author's research draws on extensive historical sources and archaeological evidence to elucidate the complex processes and dynamics involved in state formation during ancient times in this region. This scholarly work enhances our understanding of the historical development of Uzbekistan and its pivotal role in the broader context of Central Asian civilizations.

Keywords: Early states, state formation, socio-political factors, economic factors, cultural influences, archaeological evidence, Central Asia, historical development, Bactria, Sogdiana, Khorezm.

Introduction. The first stages of management go back to ancient times. In the history of primitive society, the principles and tasks of social management took various forms, organization of regulation. [1] Control was associated with the functions of managing the internal relations of the congregation. In this way, it led to the selection of individuals who have social and economic requirements, reputation, and are distinguished from others by their personal moral qualities, practical knowledge and experience. Urug elders and tribal leaders are elected at a meeting of community representatives ("People's Meeting"). [2,3] In the history of primitive society, the leading leader was busy with socially useful activities, and the social power based on clan-tribal customs represented a form of social organization that did not reach the status of a political state.

Ancient states had different characteristics and historical laws in their stages of development. First of all, the first states were formed where productive forms of economy - farming and animal husbandry were developed earlier. [4]

In primitive history (in the period of the breeding community), the location of the population was determined by blood-kinship ties. Only members of one clan lived in one or another area. The development of economic production forms led to the expansion of the population settlement areas and the continuous development of foreign relations. The need for production and other economic factors required it. [5,6] Thus, the process of mixed settlement of the population began. In this case, representatives of different clans lived in one area. Thus, a new territorial organization of the society was created. Instead of the kinship community, a territorial neighborhood community appeared, and large families that could provide themselves economically appeared.

Results. It is an urgent task to study the issue of the emergence of the first statehood in the history of the Uzbek people, the peoples of Central Asia and their ancestors. The development of irrigated agriculture and specialized crafts in the Bronze Age laid the foundation for the first state system in Central Asia. It should be noted separately that the process of transition to the state system in Central Asia was not only dependent on internal reasons, but also on highly developed traditional historical-cultural ties in the East. High-quality gold, silver and bronze objects found in Bactria testify to the development of foreign trade and mutual relations. [7] The problem of cultural relations with the state centers of the Ancient Near East is a hot topic, and archeological data shows the existing technology and economic influence of mutual relations.

The territorial base of the first states was formed by neighboring agricultural districts located close to each other. The areas appropriated for the purpose of farming are densely populated, and they were called ancient farming districts-oases. In each of them, in addition to the fertile lands and irrigation system, there were houses - fortifications and settlements, uncultivated lands and pastures. The structure of ancient agricultural districts was related to the natural-geographical, socio-economic and cultural environment. Several districts made up the region. [8]

In this way, the process of transition to the first statehood began. The second stage is related to the complete subordination of the community's self-governing institutions to the authority of the leader, and in this process, the legal order of internal and external relations between the members of the community is further improved. This situation leads to the legal regulation of various tasks in the state system and the legal formalization of power. [9,10]

The work of the members of the initially free community occupies an important place in the production activities of the first nations. The growth of the population and the need to have areas where new people can settle, gray lands and pastures for cattle, and rich resources of minerals have caused wars, big or small. In the conditions of constant military conflicts, some states have been crushed, while others have become stronger. Countless captives and devastated community members were condemned to slavery. [11] Their work was widely used for production purposes. In this way, in history, states with a medium area such as Ancient Egypt and Assyria (middle kingdoms) later became large, world-scale states such as the Achaemenid Empire.

The first states in Uzbekistan emerged on the basis of urban centers formed due to the separation of economically specialized crafts from agriculture. The importance of urban centers increased, especially during military conflicts, when they were used as shelters for district residents and shelters for herds of livestock, which formed the basis of social property.

The transition to the first state system in the territory of Uzbekistan begins in the Bronze Age. The study of the monuments of the Ulanbulaksay-Sherabad ancient agricultural oasis in Surkhandarya (Sopolli, Djarkutan) revealed the high level of development of agriculture, architecture and crafts. [12] The separate temple located in Djarkutan, like the places of worship in the Ancient East, had the essence of a

worship-economic complex, in addition to its religious function. In the Bronze Age, special social groups - priests - appeared, which organized and performed religious traditions.

In the 9th-8th centuries BC, the pastoral tribes of the steppes switched to the form of nomadic pastoralism. Nomads made great strides in the development of weaponry, archery, and mounted warfare, and settled agriculture became a very dangerous force for the population. [13] During this period, the status of cavalry-warriors and military leaders increases. In this way, associations of nomadic tribes based on the principles of "military democracy" are formed. The center of a similar association is located in the steppes of the Lower and Middle Syr Darya basin. In the 7th-6th centuries BC, a military union of Sak-Massaget tribes located in the area between the Eastern Caspian and the Southern and Eastern Aral Seas appeared.

It should be noted that the emergence and development of the first states in the ancient East have many common aspects. That is why the emergence of the first states in Central Asia is inextricably linked with the history of the states of the Ancient East. [14]

As early as the Bronze Age, farming and animal husbandry based on artificial irrigation formed the basis of the Central Asian economy. Highly productive forms of irrigated agriculture have brought about decisive changes in society. [16,17] In particular, as a result of the development of agriculture and animal husbandry, forms of additional products and private property appeared.

In Central Asia, state associations form and develop along the Amudarya (upper, middle, lower) streams, where artificial irrigation is somewhat convenient, in the Murgob oasis, Zarafshan and Kashkadarya oases. We can observe this situation in the case of the first countries in world history - Egypt (Nile) and Mesopotamia (Tigris and Euphrates).

Conclusion. The problems of the emergence of the first urban centers are a topic inextricably linked with the issues of the emergence of statehood. The first written sources do not provide relatively accurate information about the emergence of states in Central Asia. At this point, the importance of archaeological data is incomparable.

In the Bronze Age, the specialization of handicrafts and their development as a separate economic branch was important for the economic development of the society, and it stimulated the increase of additional products, which were important for the emergence of statehood, the basis of which were the first cities. In the emergence of the first states, mutual exchange, trade and cultural-economic relations in the first cities were extremely important. By the Late Bronze Age, trade and cultural contacts between the nomadic herding tribes in the north and the settled agricultural population in the south intensified. The many similarities in the findings from the southern and northern regions indicate mutual economic and cultural relations between these regions, and the development of ancient roads.

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